

Lanthanide Iodide and Perchlorate Complexes of 4-N-(2'-Hydroxybenzylidene)aminoantipyrine

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Eighteen new complexes of lanthanide iodides and perchlorates with 4-N-(2'-hydroxybenzylidene)aminoantipyrine (HBAAP) have been prepared and characterized. They have the general formulae, $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAAP})_2\text{I}]_2$, where Ln = La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y, and $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAAP})_n](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, where n = 4 for La, Pr and Nd, and n = 5 for Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y. Conductance studies indicate 1 : 2 electrolytic behaviour for the iodide complexes and 1 : 3 electrolytic behaviour for the perchlorate complexes. The magnetic moments of all the complexes agree well with Van Vleck values. Their infrared spectra reveal that HBAAP acts as a bidentate neutral ligand, one of the iodides is coordinated and none of the perchlorates is coordinated. Electronic spectra of the Nd complexes show weak covalency in the lanthanide-ligand bond. Thermogravimetric studies of the complexes indicate that these complexes are stable upto 200° and undergo complete decomposition in the range 200-620° forming the respective stable lanthanide oxides.

IN the earlier communication¹, we have reported on the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of 4-N-(2'-hydroxybenzylidene)aminoantipyrine (HBAAP) with lanthanide nitrates. In this communication we report on our studies of the complexes of HBAAP with lanthanide iodides and perchlorates. The iodide complexes are very interesting that one of the iodide ions is coordinated to the metal ion.

Experimental

Reagents: The iodides or perchlorates of La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y were prepared by dissolving the respective oxides (99.9% pure) in 50% hydroiodic acid or perchloric acid and crystallising the salts on evaporation of the solution on a water bath. HBAAP was prepared from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde by the method reported earlier^{1,2}.

Preparation and analysis of complexes: The lanthanide iodide complexes were prepared as follows. Lanthanide iodide (2 mmol) and HBAAP (12 mmol) in hot methanol were mixed and the resulting solution was kept under reflux for 1 h. The black viscous mass obtained on concentration of the solution was washed several times with hot benzene to remove the excess ligand. The solid complex separated was recrystallised by dissolving it in the minimum amount of methanol and stirring vigorously with the addition of diethyl ether. The complex separated was dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 . The perchlorate complexes were prepared by the same method as in the case of the iodide complexes except that acetone was used as the solvent instead of methanol. All these complexes

were analysed for metal, iodide and perchlorate by the conventional methods³⁻⁵.

Physical methods: The physical methods used in the present investigation were the same as described earlier¹. The far-infrared spectra were recorded on a Fourier far-ir spectrophotometer using KBr disc technique.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes show that the iodide complexes have the general formula $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAAP})_2\text{I}]_2$, where Ln = La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y, and the perchlorate complexes have the formula $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAAP})_n(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$, where n = 4 for Ln = La, Pr and Nd, and n = 5 for Ln = Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Y. All these complexes are mushroom coloured non-hygroscopic solids soluble in polar solvents, like acetone, acetonitrile, methanol and ethanol and insoluble in solvents of low polarity, like benzene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform.

The molar conductance values (Table 1) of the iodide complexes in nitrobenzene show 1 : 2 electrolytic behaviour^{6,7}. The iodide complexes dissociate slightly in acetonitrile giving values slightly higher than those expected for 1 : 2 electrolytes^{6,7}. But in the more polar solvent methanol they show 1 : 3 electrolytic behaviour^{6,7}, which is due to displacement of the coordinated iodide by methanol molecule⁶. The perchlorate complexes show 1 : 3 electrolytic behaviour in all of these solvents^{7,8}. Thus, the iodide and perchlorate complexes may be formulated as $[\text{Ln}(\text{HBAAP})_2\text{I}]_2$ and $[\text{Ln}$

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC DATA OF LANTHANIDE IODIDE AND PERCHLORATE COMPLEXES OF HBAAP

Sl. no.	Compound	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance*			μ_{eff} B. M.
		Metal	Anion	$C_6H_5NO_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	
1.	$[La(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	6.84 (6.76)	18.41 (18.53)	38.58	320.8	245.0	—
2.	$[Pr(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	6.97 (6.85)	18.86 (18.51)	42.00	324.7	249.2	3.51
3.	$[Nd(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.06 (7.01)	18.04 (18.48)	40.64	318.3	242.3	3.64
4.	$[Sm(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.19 (7.28)	18.56 (18.43)	39.05	318.9	250.4	1.66
5.	$[Gd(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.58 (7.59)	18.51 (18.37)	40.35	322.9	257.8	7.81
6.	$[Tb(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.40 (7.66)	18.13 (18.35)	43.56	317.8	247.2	9.65
7.	$[Dy(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.92 (7.82)	18.51 (18.32)	41.32	322.7	242.4	10.61
8.	$[Ho(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	7.79 (7.93)	18.27 (18.30)	40.35	321.3	240.8	10.25
9.	$[Y(HBAAP)_2]I_2$	4.39 (4.44)	19.15 (18.99)	41.76	319.4	247.3	—
10.	$[La(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.18 (8.34)	17.03 (17.92)	62.03	400.9	251.6	—
11.	$[Pr(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.42 (8.45)	17.58 (17.90)	62.85	436.5	249.6	3.59
12.	$[Nd(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.68 (8.64)	17.96 (17.86)	61.36	390.1	255.3	3.49
13.	$[Sm(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	7.60 (7.58)	14.81 (15.04)	70.46	434.7	252.7	1.56
14.	$[Gd(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.09 (7.90)	14.60 (14.99)	68.72	435.3	254.6	7.82
15.	$[Tb(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	7.91 (7.98)	14.96 (14.98)	69.79	401.8	257.5	9.66
16.	$[Dy(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.02 (8.14)	14.97 (14.95)	63.28	432.7	256.8	10.23
17.	$[Ho(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	8.03 (8.25)	14.77 (14.93)	64.51	413.5	253.4	10.58
18.	$[Y(HBAAP)_2](ClO_4)_2$	4.53 (4.63)	15.54 (15.52)	63.50	414.9	251.4	—

* In $\sim 10^{-3} M$ solution, $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$.

$(HBAAP)_{4/5}](ClO_4)_2$, respectively. The observed magnetic moments of all these iodide and perchlorate complexes agree well with the Van Vleck values⁹, which suggests that the 4f electrons in these complexes do not participate in bond formation.

The important infrared spectral bands of the complexes are presented in Table 2. The broad medium band around $3440 cm^{-1}$ attributed to the OH stretching vibration of the phenolic group¹⁰ of HBAAP does not undergo appreciable shift in all of these complexes. The phenolic C-O stretching band¹¹ at $1310 cm^{-1}$ in HBAAP is also not shifted appreciably in the spectra of the complexes. Thus, the phenolic oxygen is not coordinated to the lanthanide ion. The very strong carbonyl stretching band at $1655 cm^{-1}$ in HBAAP is shifted to lower frequency by $\sim 50 cm^{-1}$ in these complexes, indicating that the carbonyl oxygen is coordinated⁹. The strong band at $1590 cm^{-1}$ in HBAAP due to hydrogen-bonded C=N stretching vibration¹² is shifted to lower frequency by $\sim 20 cm^{-1}$. This indicates coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the central lanthanide ion with consequent decrease in carbon-nitrogen bond order¹³⁻¹⁵. Thus, HBAAP acts as a bidentate neutral ligand in all these

complexes, coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen forming a five-membered ring.

The far-infrared spectra of the iodide complexes show a strong band around $160 cm^{-1}$ which is not present in the spectrum of the free ligand. This band is assigned to the metal-iodide stretching vibration¹⁶⁻¹⁸. This result confirms the coordination of one of the iodide ions to the metal ion. The appearance of two unsplit bands in the infrared spectra of the perchlorate complexes, a strong one at $\sim 1085 cm^{-1}$ (ν_3) and a medium one at $\sim 620 cm^{-1}$ (ν_4) indicates that the perchlorate group is not coordinated in these complexes¹⁹.

The electronic spectra of these complexes in acetonitrile show a very broad band in the visible region with absorption maximum around $17.54 kK$ which may be assigned to the very strong ligand to metal charge transfer transition. Most of the bands due to f-f transition of the lanthanide ions could not be located in the visible region in the present complexes. This is due to the fact that the f-f bands are very weak and that they are masked by the very broad charge transfer band that spreads over the whole visible region²⁰.

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) AND THERMAL DECOMPOSITION DATA OF LANTHANIDE IODIDE AND PERCHLORATE COMPLEXES OF HBAAP

Sl. no.	Compound	ν_{C-O}	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu^*(ClO_4)$	ν_{Ln-I} or $\nu^*(ClO_4)$	Decomp. temp. from TG °C
1.	[La(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1605 vs	1575 vs		161 s	200
2.	[Pr(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1605 vs	1570 vs		160 s	220
3.	[Nd(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1605 vs	1570 vs		162 s	200
4.	[Sm(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1605 vs	1570 vs		159 s	200
5.	[Gd(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1600 vs	1570 vs		160 s	200
6.	[Tb(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1610 vs	1570 vs		163 s	200
7.	[Dy(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1610 vs	1565 vs		160 s	240
8.	[Ho(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1605 vs	1570 vs		160 s	220
9.	[Y(HBAAP) ₆ I]I ₂	1610 vs	1570 vs		160 s	240
10.	[La(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1575 vs	1085 vs	620 m	220
11.	[Pr(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1570 vs	1085 vs	620 m	200
12.	[Nd(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1570 vs	1090 vs	620 m	200
13.	[Sm(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1565 vs	1085 vs	620 m	200
14.	[Gd(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1600 vs	1570 vs	1080 vs	620 m	200
15.	[Tb(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1575 vs	1090 vs	620 m	220
16.	[Dy(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1605 vs	1575 vs	1090 vs	620 m	200
17.	[Ho(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1600 vs	1575 vs	1090 vs	620 m	220
18.	[Y(HBAAP) ₆](ClO ₄) ₃	1600 vs	1575 vs	1090 vs	620 m	200

m = medium; vs = very strong; s = strong.

However, in the Nd iodide and perchlorate complexes, the following f-f bands are observed, the tentative assignments of which are given in brackets. Nd iodide complex :

19.08 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{7/2}); 17.24 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{5/2}, ²G_{7/2}); 13.44 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴F_{7/2}); and 12.48 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ²H_{9/2}).

Nd perchlorate complex :

19.08 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{7/2}); 17.21 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{5/2}, ²G_{7/2}); 13.42 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴F_{7/2}); and 12.50 kK(⁴I_{9/2} → ²H_{9/2}).

A small red-shift is observed in these f-f bands compared to the aquo ion^{21,22}. Sinha covalency parameters²¹ calculated for these two Nd complexes ($\delta=0.7049$ for the iodide complex and $\delta=0.7354$ for the perchlorate complex) show weak covalency in the lanthanide-ligand bond.

Thermogravimetric data (Table 2) of the complexes show that all the complexes are stable upto ~200°. All the iodide complexes undergo decomposition in two stages as denoted by the two well-defined DTG peaks around 250-325° and 430-450°. All the perchlorate complexes undergo

decomposition in three stages as represented by the DTG peaks around 270-325°, 390-430° and 470-495°. The decomposition of all the iodide and perchlorate complexes is complete in the range 480-620° leaving behind the respective stable lanthanide oxides.

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